

In low temperature areas, some farmers prefer panicle weight type rice because panicles are harvested individually. The 1981 International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) planted in Korea was analyzed to determine if high yields result from high panicle number or large spikelet number per panicle.

High yields resulted from high panicle number (10-12/hill) (Table 1). However, both panicle weight and panicle number types can produce large yields. Suweon 306 and IR9129-169-3-2-3-3 yielded high because they had many panicles per hill

Table 2. Grain yield, number of panicles per hill, and number of spikelets per panicle of high yielding IRCTN entries. Chuncheon, Korea, 1981.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	Panicle number	Total spikelets	Fertility (%)	Flowering date
T1668	7.16	6.0	196	91	1 Aug
Barkat	6.18	8.2	150	89	28 Jul
IR15924-265-3	8.94	8.2	135	84	18 Aug
IR9224-K1	9.49	13.0	140	95	31 Jul
AC3828	8.63	13.0	127	94	5 Aug
C11561-1	8.05	13.4	112	95	11 Aug
IR9129-169-3-2-3-3	6.18	17.0	124	84	7 Aug
Suweon 306	6.86	18.4	115	76	18 Aug

(Table 2). T1668 and Barkat, from mountain regions, produced large yields from big panicles. IR9224-K1, an IRRI

line reselected in Kashmir, India, has high panicle and spikelet numbers and yielded the highest.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Testing for sheath blight resistance in rice

N. Shobha Rani and K. Satyanarayana, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 30, India

Rice sheath blight (ShB), caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn [*Thanetophorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk.], occurs during wet season in parts of Kerala, Andhra Pradesh (A. P.), and West Bengal. In 1979 a severe outbreak occurred on BPT1235 and MTU6024 in West Godavari district, A. P.

Chemical control is the only way to arrest ShB. Resistant short-statured rice varieties need to be developed.

A program to breed high yielding varieties with ShB resistance was initiated

at AICRIP, Hyderabad, during 1979 kharif. Fifty-eight entries were field tested. Plants were inoculated by typhabit method at maximum tillering. Thirty-seven varieties were moderately resistant; scores ranged from 3.0 to 5.0. During 1980 kharif moderately resistant entries were retested in two 3.75-m rows flanked by the susceptible check variety Taichung Native 1. High humidity (RH 95%) created by overhead sprinklers induced maximum disease. Only 11 varieties showed resistant reaction (score 1.0 to 3.0) in high humidity (see table). OS4 and IR42 were scored as resistant, confirming 1979 results. IET4699 was resistant, Guyana sel. 60-283 and Pankaj were moderately resistant.

Eight thousand F₄ plants from three

crosses — RP1821 (OS4/ RPW6-I7), RP1819 (Pankaj/RP1821), and RP1822 (Pankaj/ IET5656) — were field tested under favorable conditions. RP1821 crosses were most promising — 189 plants scored highly resistant (0.0 and 1.0). Among those, 76 lines were uniform. They are being tested in a replicated yield trial at AICRIP headquarters during the 1982 dry season and at Maruteru, West Godavari, reported to be a ShB hot spot, to reconfirm disease reaction.

Tetep: a potential source of resistance to rice dwarf in Nepal

B. P. Upadhyay, assistant plant pathologist, National Rice Improvement Project, Par-nipur, Nepal; and D. B. Lapis, associate professor of Plant Pathology, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, Philippines (presently, senior research fellow, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI)

In 1977 rice dwarf virus (RD) was discovered in Taichung 176 and KT32-2 (a locally bred line) at Khumaltar Station in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. *Nephotetix nigropictus*, the predominant green leafhopper species in the valley, transmits the virus. To identify potential sources of RD resistance, a preliminary screening of rice cultivars was made in the greenhouse at Khumaltar during July-September 1981. We sought to

Donor screening nursery results at AICRIP, 1980 kharif.

Entries with score ^a of					
0	1	3	5	7	9
	ET4699	IR2071-588-4		IET6774	TN1
		Guyana Sel. 60-283		RP193-1	Ram Tulsii
		ET5891	T141	ARC15762	
		ET6770	Ta-poo-cho-z	IR2071-588-5	
		Pankaj	IET6234	La ka	
		IR42	IR1103-15-8		
		OS4	Nang Payah		
		ET6235	Ramadja	Phourel	
		IET6272	IET7043	Morangedo	
		Saibham	IET7109	Phekaudu	
			Athebu	Morang Chaeran	
			Mamte	Bag Murali	
			Suduwee		

^a 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves and some plants killed.